

Average scores for reaction to RYMV at 90 DT of 60 varieties at AIRS, Kisumu, Kenya. 1989-91.

Variety	1989 LR ^a	1989 SR ^b	1990 LR ^a	1991 LR ^a	Av ^c	
Azucena	5	6	6	8	6.3	MS
Basmati 370	0	2	3	3	2	R
Basmati 217	0	2	3	3	2	R
BG35-2	7	7	5	7	6.5	S
BR51-282-8	7	8	7	8	7.5	S
BR153-2B-282-8	7	6	8	8	7.3	S
BRIRGA409	6	7	6	9	7	S
BW196	7	6	8	7	7	S
BW348-1	7	6	7	8	7	S
C1321-9	7	8	6	8	7.3	S
C1322-28	7	6	7	8	7	S
CR126-42-2	7	7	7	9	7.5	S
Elko	8	6	6	6	6.5	S
Faro 15	7	7	7	8	7.3	S
Faro 27	7	7	5	7	6.5	S
Farox 228-3-1-1	7	7	7	9	7.5	S
Farox 233-1-1-3	7	4	7	8	6.5	S
Farox 233-7-1-2	6	6	6	5	5.8	MS
Farox 239-1-1-1	7	6	5	7	6.3	S
IET6279	7	7	7	8	7.3	S
IR50	7	6	6	8	6.8	S
IR2793-80-1	5	6	6	9	6.5	S
IR9202-5-2-2-2	8	8	8	9	8.3	S
IR9698-16-3-2	6	6	8	7	6.8	S
IR9758-K2	8	6	5	8	6.8	S
IR9784-142-1-3-3	7	6	7	7	6.8	S
IR13260-100-1E-P2	6	6	8	7	6.8	S
IR19090-136-2-2-3	7	6	5	5	5.8	MS
IR19225-142-1-6	7	6	5	7	6.3	S
IR19225-289-3-1-3	8	8	6	7	7.3	S
IR24486-166-2-3	5	8	6	7	6.5	S
IR25873-22-3	7	6	5	8	6.5	S
IR27301-154-3	7	5	6	8	6.5	S
IR27301-62-2	7	7	7	8	7.3	S
ITA21	8	9	8	7	8	S
ITA222	7	8	5	8	7	S
ITA245	8	7	7	8	7.5	S
ITA249	5	6	7	9	6.8	S
ITA302	7	6	6	7	6.5	S
ITA310	4	6	3	8	5.3	MS
JC99	7	7	8	9	7.8	S
K39-96-1-1-1-2	7	7	6	8	7	S
K143-1-2	4	6	3	9	5.5	MS
KAU166	6	6	3	7	5.5	MS
Ketan1	5	4	4	3	4	MR
Kisuke	2	0	2	2	1.5	R
Khao Dawk Mall	3	0	3	3	2.3	R
Malagkit Sungsong	4	4	4	4	4	MR
Milyang 49	6	6	7	8	6.8	S
RP1125-1526-2-2-3	5	5	5	7	5.5	MS
Shin-al	7	5	4	5	5.3	MS
Sindano	9	9	9	9	9	HS
SI-PI-692033	8	7	6	8	7.3	S
TNAU658	7	8	5	8	7	S
TOX714-1-204-1-101	7	7	6	6	6.3	S
TOX902-42-1	6	4	6	7	5.8	MS
TOX902-5-103-3-101	7	6	5	8	6.5	S
TOX894-28-201-1-5	8	6	5	8	6.8	S
TOX894-28-201-1-2	8	9	6	8	7.8	S
UPR254-35-3-2	5	6	6	8	6.3	S
Total	378	365	350	431		
Mean	6	6	6	7		
F-test for variety comparison		0.29 %				
CV		16 %				
SED		0.7 %				
LSD (5%)		1.4 %				
LSD (1%)		1.9 %				

^aLR = long rainy season. ^bSR = short rainy season. ^cR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

spreader variety, was planted at 60- × 20-cm spacing. The test varieties were transplanted in three rows inside the Sindano rows at 21 d after sowing. Plants were inoculated at 18 d after transplanting (DT).

A mixture of 100 g infected leaves ground in 1 liter of distilled water with 5 ml of a phosphate buffer (to maintain pH 7.0) and 2 g of a carborundum powder (an abrasive) was used to inoculate the Sindano plants. The finger rubber technique was used, where fingers are dipped in the inoculum and then rubbed gently on all of the plants' leaves two to three times. RYMV symptoms were scored systematically using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* at 42 DT, 56 DT, 70 DT, and 90 DT.

Ketan 1 and Malagkit Sungsong were moderately resistant while Basmati 370, Basmati 217, Kisuke, and Khao Dawk Mali were resistant (see table). Nine varieties were moderately susceptible. Sindano was highly susceptible. ■

Identifying resistance genes for bacterial blight in Chengte 232

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We analyzed the bacterial blight resistance genes and their allelism for Chengte 232 and its resistance donors, using the pathogen strains W1, P1 (PXO 61, Philippines), and T1 (Japan). Chengte 232 and its resistant donors, Nongken 58 and Hongkewan, were all resistant to the three isolates; its other donor, Tetep, was resistant to T1 but susceptible to W1 and P1. Near-isogenic lines carrying known genes, CBB3(*Xa-3*) and CBB4(*Xa-4*), were resistant to these isolates. Nonghu 6, which is susceptible to the isolates, served as the susceptible parent.

To determine the number of resistance genes effective against the isolates tested, Chengte 232, Nongken 58, and Tetep were each crossed with Nonghu 6. We also crossed Chengte 232 with Tetep and Nongken 58, and Chengte 232 and Nongken 58 with CBB3 and CBB4 to test allelism of resistance genes.

Table 1. Reaction of resistance to W1, P1, and/or T1 isolates in progeny of resistant/susceptible combinations.

Combination	F ₁	F ₂			Expected ratio	χ ² _c	P
		Total	Resistant plants (no.)	Susceptible plants (no.)			
Chengte 232/Nonghu 6	RRR ^a	212	195	17	15:1	0.8503	0.50-0.25
Nongken 58/Nonghu 6	RRR ^a	196	148	48	3:1	0.0068	>0.90
Tetep/Nonghu 6	R ^b	180	168	12	15:1	0.0059	>0.90

^aThe first letter stands for reaction to W1, the second to P1, and the third to T1. ^bReaction to T1.

Table 2. Segregation for resistance to W1, P1, or T1 isolates in progeny of resistant/resistant combinations.

Combination	F ₁	F ₂			Expected ratio	χ ² _c	P
		Total	Resistant plants (no.)	Susceptible plants (no.)			
Chengte 232/Nonghu 58	RR ^a	204	204	0			
Chengte 232/Tetep	R ^b	306	300	6	255:1	15.5633	<0.005
Chengte 232/CBB 3	RR ^c	188	188	0			
Nongken 58/CBB 3	RR ^c	204	204	0			
Chengte 232/CBB 4	RR ^a	195	190	5	63:1	0.7040	0.50-0.25
Nongken 58/CBB 4	RR ^a	210	195	15	15:1	0.1537	0.75-0.50

^aThe first letter stands for reaction to W1, the second to P1. ^bReaction to T1. ^cThe first letter stands for reaction to W1, the second to T1.

All materials were planted in the field and inoculated at the booting stage (after dipping scissors into a bacterial suspension containing 10⁹ cells/ml). Different tillers were inoculated with the different isolates and marked with different colors. Disease reaction was assessed after 3 wk using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Plants with scores of 1-3 were classified as resistant and those with scores of 4-9 as susceptible.

Chengte 232 and Tetep each carried two resistance genes for these isolates, while Nongken 58 carried one (Table 1). Allelism tests indicated one of the two genes in Chengte 232 was allelic to Xa-3, which was derived from Nongken 58. Apparently, the resistance genes of Tetep were not transferred into Chengte 232 (Table 2). The other gene of Chengte 232, however, was probably derived from Kongkewan ■

Analysis of resistance gene for blast in Chengte 232

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We analyzed the resistance genes and their allelism of Chengte 232 and its resistance donors using blast fungus isolates ZB1 (926) and P-2b (Japan). Chengte 232 and its resistance donors, Toride 1 and Tetep, are resistant to ZB1 and P-2b. Nonghu 6, which is susceptible to the isolates, was used as the susceptible parent.

Chengte 232, Toride 1, and Tetep were each crossed with Nonghu 6 to analyze the inheritance of resistance. We also made crosses among Chengte 232, Toride 1, and Tetep to test allelism of resistance genes.

All materials were planted in the field and inoculated at maximum tillering by injecting plants with a spore suspension of 1-2 x 10⁵ conidia/ml. Disease reaction was assessed at 7 d after inoculation using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Plants with scores of 1-3 were classified as resistant and those with

Table 1. Resistance reaction to ZB1 and P-2b races in progeny of resistant/susceptible combinations.

Combination	Race	F ₁	F ₂			Expected ratio	χ ² _c	P
			Total	Resistant	Susceptible			
Chengte 232/Nonghu 6	ZB1	R ^a	189	143	46	3:1	0.0159	>0.90
	P-2b	R	189	143	46	3:1	0.0159	>0.90
Toride 1/Nonghu 6	ZB1	R	204	144	60	3:1	1.8889	0.25-0.10
	P-2b	R	204	144	60	3:1	1.8889	0.25-0.10
Tetep/Nonghu 6	ZB1	R	182	133	49	3:1	0.2637	0.75-0.50
	P-2b	R	182	166	16	15:1	1.5956	0.25-0.10

^aR = resistant.

Table 2. Segregation for resistance to ZB1 and P-2b races in progeny of resistant/resistant combinations.

Combination	Race	F ₁	F ₂			Expected ratio	χ ² _c	P
			Total	Resistant	Susceptible			
Chengte 232/Toride 1	ZB1	R ^a	216	216	0			
	P-2b	R	216	216	0			
Chengte 232/Tetep	ZB1	R	169	162	7	15:1	0.9471	0.50-0.25
	P-2b	R	169	165	4	63:1	0.2841	0.75-0.50
Toride 1/Tetep	ZB1	R	178	168	10	15:1	0.0375	0.90-0.75
	P-2b	R	178	170	8	63:1	8.1330	<0.005

^aR = resistant.

scores of 4-9 as susceptible.

A single dominant gene controls resistance to ZB1 and P-2b in Chengte 232 and Toride 1. Tetep has one dominant gene for resistance to ZB1 and

two dominant duplicate genes for P-2b (Table 1). Allelism tests indicated that the genes of Chengte 232 are nonallelic to those of Tetep and those of Toride 1 are allelic (Table 2).